

THE TECHNIQUES OF DEVELOPING GRAMMAR SUB-SKILLS

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Annotation: This article provides information about cognitive aspect of acquiring grammar mechanisms and presents the techniques of developing grammar sub-skills and principles of teaching grammar.

Key words: grammar, grammar sub-skills, generalization, grammar exercises, presentation, training.

To teach grammar, you need explicit as well as implicit knowledge, to be confident about using the correct terms and explaining these. Don't just learn the next term you are teaching. It is important to be able to relate new learning to other features and the text as a whole. Give talk a high priority in your classroom. There are a number of reasons why there occur different concepts about "grammar" when one comes across this term. While it is perceived as a part of Linguistics in the course of mother tongue at the secondary school, in teaching/learning foreign language it is considered to be the grammatical side of the speech. According to various scientific sources the word "grammar" could be limited in two notions: 1) the grammatical side of the speech – structural organization of ideas in speaking, listening, reading and writing e.g., using articles; speech patterns; verb forms of the person adequately to the context) and (grammar phenomenon and abstractions e.g., the first place of the subject in the sentence; the plural form of the noun). The process of developing grammar sub-skills consists of three stages:

1.presentation 2.training 3.using

Presentation of grammar material happens inductively or deductively. Inductive presentation begins from example and transfers to abstraction; deductive one presents a rule (or a speech pattern) then practices examples. Rule — generalization appears when there are more than one example. Only one grammar unit can be learned without rule on the level of vocabulary (try and remember so-called "lexical approach"). Also in mostly used grammar phenomena the only example is given lexically. Many factors should be taken into consideration while introducing new grammar phenomenon to students: Factor of relation to the nature of grammar phenomenon. Similarity of

the form, easiness of clear meaning requires using inductive method. Factor of similarity and difference between native and foreign language cases. Similarity makes to use induction and difference makes to use deduction. Factor of leaning to the experience gained in the foreign language. Factor of learning microunits of new phenomenon via different methods. Using inductive and deductive methods must be rational. Organizational part of presentation stage involves three sequent methodological actions: presentation, control of perception and memorizing a new unit as well as uttering to perform initial exercises. Doing exercises promotes transformation of grammar units into foreign language skill Grammar sub-skill is a complex of operations and acts that provides proper and automatized usage and memorization of morphologic-syntactic units of speech. Morphologic sub-skill involves formation and usage, operation and acts of forms (noun suffixes, verb suffixes, grammar units that came before noun, e.g. articles, prepositions, etc.). Syntactic sub-skill includes word order, formation of word combinations. The sub-skill of using grammar material is made up by changing words and inserting the words into place. Development of learners' speech skills is characterized by the process "stamping" of grammar units. The stage of doing exercises consists of three parts: 1. Learning to utter grammar phenomena imitatively, any grammar act is limited by leaning to its sample. Performing imitative exercise binds to the next part. 2. Doing exercises by making changes in the content of imitatively learned units. The familiar material serves to thorough acquiring the new grammar phenomenon. 3. The previously learnt and today's grammar units are used in oral and written forms of expression. The speech orientation is common to the given time of doing exercises.

Since grammar sub-skills are developed as reproductive and receptive skills of oral and written speech, they affect FL acquisition. Consequently, acquiring grammar mechanisms cannot be excluded from the control level of formation of professional foreign language communicative competence as the grammatical component is an integral part of foreign language communicative competence. Moreover, at non-language Universities grammar material must always be related to the lexical material, which is presented in the framework of specialization and future professional activities.

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